

A Semi-Autonomous Surgical Manipulation Task performed by a Cognitive Robotic System

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Abstract—The development of robotic systems with a certain level of autonomy to be used in critical scenarios, such as an operating room, necessarily requires a seamless integration of multiple state-of-the-art technologies. In this paper we propose a cognitive robotic architecture that is able to help an operator accomplish a specific task. The architecture integrates an action recognition module to understand the scene, a supervisory control to make decisions, and a model predictive control to plan collision-free trajectory for the robotic arm taking into account obstacles and model uncertainty. The proposed approach has been validated on a simplified scenario involving only a da Vinci[®] surgical robot and a novel manipulator holding standard laparoscopic tools.

Index Terms—Surgical Robotics; Action Recognition; Collision Avoidance; Model Predictive Control

I. INTRODUCTION

A semi-autonomous robotic system for surgery represents one of the final steps in the transition through the increasingly complex levels of cognition and decision-making that will transform robots executing repetitive tasks into robots cooperating with humans proactively [1], all while leaving full control to the user. These robots will encompass improved dexterity and perception to enhance their cooperation capabilities through advanced cognitive systems, all under supervision of performance monitoring systems [2] [3]. This preliminary work falls within the scope of the EU project SARAS, which is the acronym for Smart Autonomous Robotic Assistant Surgeon: the aim is to produce an autonomous system that combines perception, cognition and control to aid a main surgeon during complex operations by responding to both verbal and non-verbal commands. The preliminary results presented here have been obtained by using the SARAS platform to execute a cooperative robotic surgical training task performed by a teleoperator and the autonomous robot.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The system developed for testing the human-robot cooperative task is composed of three main blocks:

- an action recognition module, which analyses the video stream coming from the endoscope and assigns to each

Fig. 1. Overview of the SARAS solo-surgery platform architecture.

frame the corresponding action label and confidence level, thus identifying the states of changing actions;

- a supervisory control, implemented as a Finite State Machine, that monitors the overall system status and solves conflicts between perception and control.
- a model predictive control (MPC), which evaluates the desired next kinematic state for the controlled robot according to the confidence level of the action recognition;

These are the basic building blocks for an autonomous system, i.e. the ability to understand the task, to plan a proper action, and to ensure its safe execution. The robot used in the task is a novel platform for laparoscopy developed for the SARAS SOLO-Surgery platform (Fig. 1). It is divided in three subsystems: a passive positioning arm with 7 DoF; an actuated head with 3 DoF and the possibility to maintain a remote centre of motion (RCM) constraint; an actuated laparoscopy tool (rotation plus gripper). The autonomous system is intended to aid the main surgeon in completing the simple training task of pick-and-place using a small plastic ring while the main surgeon operates one arm of the DaVinci surgical system in a standard teleoperation mode.

A. Action Recognition

The action recognition employs a Convolutional Neural Network [4] trained using the combined setup controlled

manually by a main surgeon (MS) and an assistant surgeon (AS), recording approximately 2000 frames at 10 frames per second of the pick-and-place task. It encompasses information about the sequencing of actions in an additional layer of the processed frame that contains a motion history image [5]. The result is a segmentation profile of the sequence of actions and the corresponding confidence profile for each one.

B. Supervisory Controller and MPC

The supervisory control addresses action recognition uncertainties as it mediates over the action recognition responses by maintaining a temporal stack of action labels and confidences that allows to mediate among them to correct erratic classifications and, thus, ensure a safe progression throughout the control states. Additionally, it processes the information coming from the target tracking system, which is based on simple 3D colour clustering on a toroid geometry, which is to be sent as a target for the MPC. The latter models the kinematics as a single integrator in the discrete time domain:

$$x(k+1) = x(k) + Bu(k)$$

where $x \in \mathbb{R}^3$ are the coordinates of the position of the end-effector in the task space, $B = \text{diag}\{\Delta t_c, \Delta t_c, \Delta t_c\}$ is the input matrix, Δt_c is the sample time ($t = k\Delta t_c$, $k \in \mathbb{Z}$) and $u \in \mathbb{R}^3$ represents the control input, namely the velocities of the end-effector.

The solution of the constrained finite-horizon optimal control problem

$$\begin{aligned} \min_u \quad & \sum_{i=0}^{p-1} (x_g(k) - \hat{x}(k+i))^T Q (x_g(k) - \hat{x}(k+i)) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \hat{x}(k+i+1) = \hat{x}(k+i) + Bu(k+i) \\ & \|u(k+i)\| \leq \alpha(k)u^{max} \\ & d_{rob}^{obst}(k+i) \geq d_{sft} \\ & i = 0, \dots, p-1 \end{aligned}$$

operates within the imposed constraints on both the optimal control velocity $u(k)$ and the obstacle distance between tools $d_{rob}^{obst}(k)$, which are represented as capsules composed by two hemispheres, centered at the remote centre of motion and the end effector, and a cylinder, with longitudinal axis linking the two points. The control velocity is, additionally, modulated using the overall confidence level of the action recognition module so that a reduced command velocity is issued whenever the confidence level α is low. This has the benefit of improving safety while maintaining liveness in the system, a lack of which could hinder both the task and its cognition.

III. RESULTS

The task consists in exchanging a red colored plastic ring between a da Vinci[®] laparoscopic tool teleoperated by the surgeon and the autonomous SARAS arm holding a standard laparoscopic tool. Such tool needs to arrive at the correct location for the exchange, grasp the ring and bring it to the

Fig. 2. Experimental setup. (a) da Vinci[®] arm and SARAS arm developed by Medineering. (b) da Vinci[®] robotic tool (left) and commercial laparoscopic tool mounted on the SARAS' arm end-effector (right) as seen thanks to the 3D endoscope.

Fig. 3. Experimental result. Plot (a) shows the norm of modulated target velocity with respect to the actual robot velocity; plot (b) shows the confidence profile as evaluated by the FSM

designated drop area without, possibly, any external intervention.

The graph in Figure 3 depicts the velocity profile of the SARAS arm compared with the command issued by the MPC and the confidence level α of the action recognition.

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